

✦ Aahar in Ayurveda: Millets as a Pathya in Life style disorders; A Comprehensive review from Bhavpraksh Nighantu

PRESENTATION BY,

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Aims and objectives

- To understand the concept of **Nidana Parivarjana** (eliminating causative factors) and **Prakriti Vighata** (counteracting disease pathology) in the context of **Santarpanjanya Vyadhi** through the use of millets.
- To explore the **role of millets** in managing and preventing **lifestyle disorders**, as described in **Ayurvedic texts and modern nutritional science**.
- To analyze the **properties, actions, and therapeutic indications of millets** as described in **Bhavaprakasha Nighantu (Dhanya Varga – Truna Dhanya)** and correlate them with their **clinical utility in current health challenges**.

#Loveayurvedexperienacemiracle

Thank You For Attention

"GIVE ME SIX HOURS
TO CHOP DOWN
A TREE & I WILL
SPEND THE FIRST
FOUR SHARPENING
THE AXE."

-ABRAHAM LINCOLN

